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Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science

Dr. Kanta¹

Abstract

The various references mentioned in Vedic literature reflect the development of astronomy or celestial knowledge of that time. The sages of that era were well aware of the terrestrial effects of celestial bodies, as is evident from the references described in the Rigveda. The Vedic people had a special understanding of the moon's movements. As a result, nearly all ancient civilizations' calendars were lunar-based. The study of the moon's movements led to the observation that its orbit in relation to the bright and easily recognizable stars it encountered took approximately 27 days. These 27 divisions of the moon's path were called "Nakshatras" in astrology. Although solar-based calculations were predominant during the Vedic period, the post-Vedic era saw the prevalence of nakshatra-based calculations. This implies that during this time, month names like Chaitra began to be used more frequently than names like Madhva. Mr. Tilak, in his work Orion, concluded from comparing references in the Taittiriya Samhita and the Tandya Brahmana that the term "Phalguni Purnima" from the Taittiriya Samhita had evolved to "Phalguni" in the Tandya Brahmana. However, the use of month names like Phalguna, Chaitra, and Vaishakha had not yet started at that time. Nonetheless, references in the later parts of the Shatapatha Brahmana, Kaushitaki Brahmana, Tandya Brahmana, and Panchavimsha Brahmana indicate that the usage of Chaitra and similar names began towards the end of the Brahmana period. Therefore, from the post-Vedic period and the time of Vedanga Jyotisha until the present, nakshatra-based calculations have been predominant in most calendar systems.

Keywords: Rigveda, month duration, lunar calendar, nakshatra, Arjuni, Agha, Shadvedanga, Vedanga Jyotisha, star clusters, Mrigashira, nakshatra-based.

The entire body of Indian literature is based on the Vedas, and the

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scientific interpretation of the Vedas is found in the Brahmana texts. The various references mentioned in Vedic literature reflect the development of astronomy or celestial knowledge of that time. The sages of that era were well aware of the terrestrial effects of celestial bodies, as is evident from the references described in the **Rigveda** (1.50.11). Although initially, when ancient humans focused on the horizon, the Earth and sky might have appeared to be merged, and the horizon over the seas seemed endless, leaving their curiosity about time and direction unsatisfied. Ultimately, the stars in the sky successfully resolved this curiosity, without a doubt. Just as ancient humans learned about the calculation of a fortnight by constantly observing the waxing and waning phases of the moon, they also gained knowledge of the east and west directions from sunrise and sunset. In time, they discovered that after a full moon or new moon, the return of another full moon or new moon within a fixed period, known as a month, was a regular occurrence. The Vedic people had a particular understanding of the moon's movements. As a result, nearly all ancient civilizations' calendars were lunar-based.

It is not surprising that the study of the moon's movements drew attention to the specific stars that appear in the moon's path. Consequently, ancient astronomers estimated the moon's orbit concerning these bright and easily identifiable stars to be approximately 27 days. As a result, the entire lunar path was broadly divided into 27 parts, marking these stars or constellations. These 27 segments of the lunar path are referred to as 'nakshatras' in astrology. In the **Taittiriya Brahmana** (तन्नक्षत्राणां नक्षत्रत्वम् । देवगृहा वै नक्षत्राणि । यानि वा इमानि पृथिव्याश्चित्राणि तानि नक्षत्राणि । 1.5.2), two etymologies for the term nakshatra are provided in a single instance. According to the first etymology, the directly luminous celestial bodies are referred to as 'devas' (gods), and since these celestial bodies travel in the zodiacal constellations, the nakshatras are considered the abodes of the gods. According to the second etymology, the nakshatras are referred to as images of the Earth because various types of creatures are imagined in the celestial constellations. Now, a brief observation of the form of nakshatra science in Vedic literature is warranted:

The Nature of Nakshatra Science in Vedic Literature

In the Vedic hymns, the term nakshatra is predominantly used not for a specific nakshatra, but for all stars. The term nakshatra appears only once in the Rigveda concerning the nakshatras of the lunar path (अथो नक्षत्राणामेषामुपस्थे सोम आदितः ॥ 10.85.2). In the mention of the Riksha (the Seven Sages), it is stated, “These Rikshas, which are situated in the sky and are visible at night, where do they go during the day?” Later, to clarify the appropriate meaning of the term Riksha, it is explicitly cited in the Shatapatha Brahmana as, “The Seven Sages were called Riksha first” (सप्तर्षीनुहस्म वै पुरर्क्षा इत्याचक्षते ॥ 2.1.2.4.). In the principal text of Siddhanta astrology, the Surya Siddhanta (1.25, 7.1, 9.14), the word nakshatra has four synonymous terms: nakshatra, bh, riksha, and dhishnya. Although modern astronomers believe that ancient astrologers or Vedic astronomers did not have extensive knowledge of the physical properties of the nakshatras or stars, such as their shapes, sizes, numbers, and distances, they did manage to learn a significant amount about the movements and activities of the nakshatras. A brief description of these subjects is as follows:

The Utility of Nakshatra Knowledge for Agriculture and Sacrifices

It is well known that initially, the need for astrological knowledge was felt for agriculture and sacrifices (yajna). This fact is evident from various references in Vedic literature. For example, in a verse from the Taittiriya Brahmana (1/5/1), it is mentioned that plowing is done under the Anuradha nakshatra, and concerning the Vishakha nakshatra, it is said that on one side are the pairs of plows (yuga) and on the other are the plowmen (krishamana). Thus, there is a connection between agriculture and some activity, such as sowing, planting, tilling, or harvesting, and the nakshatras. Similar references are found elsewhere as well.

In the same manner, the connection between various yajnas (sacrifices) and the nakshatras is also observed. For example, it is described in the Taittiriya Brahmana (3.1.4.6) “Brihaspati wanted to become Brahmavarchasi. He offered sweet rice made with cow’s milk to Brihaspati and Pushya... Whoever performs a yajna with this offering becomes Brahmavarchasi.” Additionally, there is a mention

in the Taittiriya Brahmana (1.1.2) about making offerings to Agni in certain nakshatras like Krittika. Furthermore, numerous places in Vedic literature indicate the significance of nakshatra knowledge for sacrifices.

Names of Nakshatras, Deities, and Gender

In the fourth, fifth, and tenth mandalas of the Rigveda (4.51.2; 5.54.13; 10.64.8), the names of nakshatras such as Chitra, Revati, Tishya (Pushya), Magha, etc., appear in various places, but the names of the 27 nakshatras are not found anywhere. In one verse of the Rigveda, the term 'Arjuni' is used for Phalguni and 'Agha' for Magha (सूर्याया वहतुः प्रागात् सवितायमवासृजत्। अघासु हन्यन्ते गावोर्जुन्योः पर्युह्यते ॥ 10.85.13). These words are not commonly found in post-Vedic literature; however, they indicate the aforementioned nakshatras from an earlier period. References in the Atharva Samhita (14.1.13) and Shatapatha Brahmana (2.1.2.11) further confirm this assertion.

In the Taittiriya Samhita (4.4.10) and the Taittiriya Brahmana, (1.5.1-2, 1.1.2, 1.1.10.6) the names of all the nakshatras, their deities, and sometimes the etymology of the names of the nakshatras, as well as their gender and number, are mentioned frequently. Additionally, the Atharva Veda (19.7.1-5) contains only the names of the nakshatras without mentioning their deities. In the foundational text of astrology included in the six Vedangas, Vedanga Jyotisha, the names of all the nakshatras and their deities are presented in a symbolic style.

Number of Nakshatras

When we look at the number of nakshatras in Vedic literature, there is no mention of 27 nakshatras in the literature from the Rigveda period. In the Taittiriya Shrutis, the mention of the Abhijit nakshatra appears only in a few places, and it is clearly not stated anywhere that the number of nakshatras is 27 or 28. In the **Shatapatha Brahmana** (10.5.45), there are 27 nakshatras and 27 upanakshatras. However, in the **Atharva Samhita**, the number of nakshatras is explicitly stated to be 28. Additionally, the treatise on **Vedic astrology**, composed by Maharishi Lagadha, also mentions the number of nakshatras as 27 (*Vedang Jyotisha-14*).

Number of Stars in the Nakshatras

As for the number of stars in the nakshatras, the word “Punarvasu,” which refers to a nakshatra, is used in the dual form in the Rigveda (7.75.5), indicating that there are two stars for Punarvasu. References to several other nakshatras such as Chitra, Revati, and others can also be found. In the Aitareya Brahmana (13.9), an interesting story about the nakshatras Vyadha, Mriga, and Rohini presents the shape of the Mrigashirsha nakshatra. Since the main ten stars are considered part of the Mrigashirsha nakshatra, a straight line forms through the three stars in the middle, representing the aforementioned Trikanḍa arrow. The four stars surrounding this line represent the four legs of the deer, and the three stars close to the top represent the head of the deer. In addition to these ten stars, there are several smaller stars around them. This entire formation is also referred to as “Orion,” which has been extensively discussed by Shri Bal Gangadhar Tilak in his book, “The Orion”.

Furthermore, the Taittiriya Brahmana also clearly mentions the number of stars in the nakshatras. For example, the term ‘Invakah’ for the Mrigashirsha nakshatra is used in the plural form, and the description of Mrigashirsha also confirms the presence of ten stars. The five stars of the Hasta nakshatra form a shape resembling a hand, which is why it is named Hasta. Among the remaining nakshatras, Rohini, Ardra, Tishya (Pushya), Chitra, Swati, Jyeshtha, Mula, Shroana, Shatabhisha, and Revati are all used in the singular form, indicating that each of these has a single star. The nakshatras Punrvasu, Purva Phalguni, Uttara Phalguni, Vishakha, and Ashvayuja are used in the dual form, suggesting they have two stars each. Additionally, Krittika, Ashlesha, Magha, Anuradha, Purva Ashadha, Uttara Ashadha, Shravana, Purva Bhadrpada, Uttara Bhadrpada, and Abhijit are all used in the plural form, implying that they have more than two stars. In the Taittiriya Brahmana (3.1.4), one place mentions seven stars for Krittika, while in another place, Shravana and Uttara Bhadrpada are said to have four stars each (Tai. Brah: 3.1.2). Although not all the nakshatras have their star counts specified in the provided references, it is certain that the study of not only nakshatras but also related star clusters had already begun in the Vedic period.

Conclusion

After all the discussions, it can be concluded that although the primary emphasis in the pre-Vedic period was on solar calculations, there is a noticeable prevalence of nakshatra-based calculations in the post-Vedic period. This implies that during this time, the terms related to the Chaitra month were more commonly used compared to those related to the Madhvaadi month. Although the Rigveda, Aitareya Brahmana, Taittiriya Samhita-Brahmana, and Vajasaneyi Samhita-Brahmana have a special significance of Madhvaadi names, the nakshatra-linked terms for Chaitra month, such as the full moon associated with the Chitra nakshatra, are not clearly visible, except for one or two mentions. These references are found in the Taittiriya Samhita (7.4.8.1-3) and Taittiriya Brahmana (1.1.2.8). Nevertheless, Mr. Tilak has drawn a conclusion in “The Orion” by comparing the references found in the Taittiriya Samhita and the Tandya Brahmana (5.9.1-14), stating that the term “Phalgun Full Moon” from the time of the Taittiriya Samhita had transformed into “Phalgun” during the period of the Tandya Brahmana (pp.34-72). However, these indications also lead to the conclusion that during the time of the Taittiriya Samhita-Brahmana, it was already recognized that the moon completes its cycle among the nakshatras, meaning that names like Phalgun, Chaitra, etc., were in circulation (The third sutra in the Tandya Brahmana gives an additional reason for rejecting the ‘Ekaṣṭaka’ while in the fourth sutra ‘Vichhinnaṃ’ is that the word ‘Phalguni- Purnamasa’ is paraphrased by ‘Phalguni’ in the 8th Sutra, thus clearly showing that the former was then understood to mean the full-moon night. - The Orion, pp.35). However, the usage of the names Phalgun, Chaitra, Vaishakha, etc., had not yet started during that period. Yes, references from the later sections of the Shatapatha Brahmana, (योऽसौवैशाखस्यामावास्यातस्यामादधीत...पशुषु प्रतिष्ठिति ।; 11.1.1.7) the Kaushitaki Brahmana, (तैषस्यामावास्याया एकाह उपरिष्ठाद्दीक्षेरन् माघस्य वेत्याहुः । ; 19.2.3) the Tandya Brahmana, (5.9.1-14) and the Panchavimsha Brahmana (मुखं वा एतत् संवत्सरस्य यत् फाल्गुनः । ; 5.9.9) certainly prove that by the end of the Brahmana period, the usage of terms related to Chaitra and others had begun.

Thus, from the post-Vedic period to the current era, nakshatra-based calculations have been predominantly utilized in the

formulation of most calendars. This statement does not imply that nakshatra-based calculations did not exist at all during the pre-Vedic period. In fact, even in ancient literature, many references to nakshatras like Agha (Magha) and Arjuni (Phalgun) are found in the context of stars and star clusters. Evidence from the Rigveda suggests that there was a sound knowledge of nakshatras and their different stars during the Vedic period. In the Taittiriya Samhita and Brahmana, a reliable form of nakshatra science is attained, where the gender, number, deities, offerings, etc., of all nakshatras are discussed. Therefore, nakshatra science is a fascinating realm. Its vastness and diversity evoke a sense of human insignificance while also instilling a sense of pride in the fact that humanity on Earth is a unique creation of this nakshatra realm.

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